

Deliverable 6.1

TITLE: PROJECT WEBSITE

Primary Author(s)	Dace Ševčenko
Work Package / Task:	WP6 / Task 6.1.
Due Date:	31/12/2023
Delivery Date:	29/12/2023
Document Status:	Final
Confidentiality:	PU
Deliverable Type:	O

* Dissemination Level: PU= public; SEN= sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; CO= confidential, only for members of the Consortium.

**Deliverable Type: R= report, document; Other= website, software, prototype etc.

AUTHORS

LEAD CONTRIBUTOR	BKUS
OTHER CONTRIBUTORS	FSJD

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR	DESCRIPTION
1	13/12/2023	Dace Ševčenko	First draft of website sent to project coordinators for review
2	15/12/2023	Dace Ševčenko	Revised website sent to all partners for review
3	22/12/2023	Dace Ševčenko	Final version of website approved by project coordinators

INTERNAL REVIEW HISTORY

REVIEWED BY	DATE	DESCRIPTION
Marja Vaitinen	13/12/2023	Sent for initial review
Katariina Gehrmann	13/12/2023	Sent for initial review
Jennifer McIntosh	13/12/2023	Sent for initial review: Reviewed for grammar, consistency in presentation of the project, and consistency in use of language throughout the sit
All partners	15/12/2023	Sent for review by all partners

Disclaimer/ Acknowledgment

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Website concept and content	4
Conclusions	4

1. Introduction

The PHEMS Project Website, phems.eu, is a key part of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). As the calling card of the project, it explains to a range of stakeholders the objectives of PHEMS, how the project is organized, and the value that the project will bring to the European Union both in terms of health outcomes and technologic advances. It also provides a clear overview of partners and how to reach work package leads and project coordinators.

2. Website concept and content

The site was designed to communicate a sense of freshness and energy, similar to a start-up company. It was also kept simple, presenting only key information that would be useful to the target audience. Language is accessible and understandable by a lay audience, while communicating the technical features that make the project unique.

The site is also designed to grow. As the project progresses sections will be added with information targeting specific stakeholders (hospitals, small and mid-sized enterprises and researchers, health systems and policy makers, as well as patient advocacy groups and the general public). There will also be a space for publications and other tools to communicate with stakeholders. These sections will be informed by the networks that are being developed as part of Task 6.3

Conclusions

The PHEMS website fully meets the requirements for D6.1 and will continue to grow as the project matures.